

Scientific Work Analysis of Michael X Cohen

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Abstract

The aim of this work is to emphasize application of open science principles and Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) in biomedical engineering research. The scientific work of Michael X Cohen, a highly cited researcher in the field, was analyzed using data extracted from OpenAlex. The dataset was processed using the RAISE platform, integrating PIDs for datasets, scripts, and experimental results. The key findings of this study include an increasing trend in open access publications over the years, contributing to the improvement of research across disciplines, as well as insights into the collaboration patterns of the selected researcher.

Keywords: Open Science, Persistent Identifiers, Biomedical Engineering, RAISE

1 Introduction

Open science practices have become increasingly important not only in the biomedical engineering field but across all scientific disciplines, as they promote transparency, reproducibility, and reliability. Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) play a crucial role in this context by providing permanent references to research objects, including datasets, software, and experimental results.

This work aims to demonstrate an open science workflow by analyzing the scientific documents of a researcher through the use of PIDs over time.

2 Methodology

This work was done following the instructions that are publicly available within the RAISE environment (Konstantinidis, 2026, "Getting started with RAISE").

2.1 Dataset Preparation

Publication data was extracted from OpenAlex using the researcher's ORCID identifier. The original dataset contained 193 publications spanning 2003-2025. For the purpose and the meaning of this work, the first 10 publications of the whole dataset were chosen as a sample. The whole dataset was uploaded to the RAISE platform using the AUTH node and assigned a persistent identifier (*Markopoulos, 2026, "MX Cohen publication dataset"*). The selection of the researcher was done based on his significant contributions to neuroscience, electrophysiology, and EEG analysis, with 127 publications in BME-related Journals and 29,897 citations.

2.2 Experimental Workflow

The analysis workflow was implemented on the RAISE platform including the following steps:

- **Processing Script:** The analysis was conducted using an already existing script (Konstantinidis, 2026, *openalex researcher work analysis*,2026), which was executed within the RAISE environment.
- **Project Setup:** A RAISE project was created integrating the dataset and the processing script.
- **Evaluation Execution:** The script was executed on the dataset within the RAISE environment, generating analysis report, figures, diagrams and extraction of metrics.
- **Results:** The results of the analysis were made publicly available within the RAISE environment (*Markopoulos, 2026,"MX Cohen evaluation v1"*).

All the objects (dataset, script, results) were assigned DOIs, ensuring long-term accessibility and reliability.

3 Results

The analysis of Michael X. Cohen's publications revealed the following key findings:

- **Open Access Trends:** The proportion of open access documents relative to the total number of publications has increased over time. OA rate increased from 51.0% prior to 2015 to 85.7% after 2020
- **Co-authorship Network:** Michael X. Cohen has collaborated with 376 unique researchers, and each paper has an average of 4 authors.

The results of the analysis of Michael X. Cohen's scientific work have been assigned a PID (*Markopoulos, 2026,"MX Cohen evaluation v1"*) and can be verified either by examining the plots or by rerunning the analysis.

4 Discussion

The analysis shows a strong increase in open access publications, from 51.0% before 2015 to 85.7% after 2020. This follows general trends in biomedical engineering, where policies and funding encourage open access.

The large collaboration network (376 collaborators) highlights the interdisciplinary nature of the research, combining neuroscience, electrophysiology, and computational methods.

This workflow demonstrates open science in practice: data and methods are accessible, results can be reproduced, and credit is properly assigned.

References

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